

Cashless Payment with Mobile Wallets: LINDDUN Privacy Threat Model

Dimitri Van Landuyt

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Cashless payment is becoming increasingly ubiquitous and with this overall trend, also the adoption of non-bank-led payment solutions keeps increasing. In this document, we provide the standalone application description of an abstracted mobile wallet based system, of which the most prevalent examples are Google Wallet or Apple Pay. These payment systems are integrated within the operating systems of mobile platforms, and tightly integrated in their overall ecosystems. The technology itself relies on hardware capabilities such as Trusted Execution Environments. The abstracted payment system described in this document is based on technical document pertaining the Apple Pay system. We first present the overall case description, consisting of two distinct Data Flow Diagrams (DFDs) and a step-by-step explanation of the main functioning of this system. Then, we present the LINDDUN privacy threat model for this case, which lists and describes the most prevalent privacy threats.

1 Introduction

This report presents a case study application of the LINDDUN privacy threat modeling framework. It is comprised of two parts: (i) an in-depth case description, and (ii) detailed threat descriptions.

Part I of this report is based on the work conducted within the context and scope of the master's thesis entitled '*LINDDUN Privacy Threat Analysis of a Mobile Payment System*' by Morganne Verhaeren,¹ supervised by Dimitri Van Landuyt, Qianying Liao and Wouter Joosen² First, a number of scoping decisions are introduced and motivated, based on the availability of technical information, popularity, etc. More concretely, a representation of a mobile payment system is chosen in Section 2. Then, Section 3 introduces the main DFD models of the application, and discusses their elements and main flows. Section 3 shows the DFDs of the system and explains these in more detail.

Part II is based on the combined threat model outputs of four distinct threat modelers: Nicolas Boltz, Ayesha Iftikhar, Alexander Vogt, and Manuel Córcoles. It consists of Section 4 which presents the resulting LINDDUN threat model for this application case.

¹ 13.

² The content presented in this report mainly corresponds to Chapter 6 of the master's thesis.

Part I

Case description

2 *Scope and inputs*

In this application case, the focus is on a payment solution integrated in a mobile wallet system. In comparison with bank-led mobile payment systems (e.g. through banking apps) mobile wallets bring involvement of additional third-party organizations, typically the mobile platform providers that offer these apps and services. Some examples of such third-party organizations involved in the mobile payment system are the wallet providers and the TSP³. The TSP generates and manages unique tokens, that are used to replace sensitive information in the mobile payment system.⁴ This in turn implies that they will also have access to information linked to data subjects.

³ Token service provider

⁴ 9, 11.

To ensure realism of the mobile payment system model, the model is based on a representative real-world system, in this case, Apple Pay.

We select a concrete solution with the predominant aim to create a representative abstraction of generic mobile wallet-based payment system. Architectural abstraction is made of vendor- and technology-specific elements where applicable, and as such the threat analysis itself does not target a specific vendor or technology. Regardless, Apple Pay was crowned the most used mobile wallet in the U.S.⁵ in 2022. In Belgium, it was stated that in 2019 Apple Pay was also used more extensively than Google Pay.⁶

⁵ 5.

⁶ 6.

Fehr et al.⁷ created a model of this mobile payment system in their work, which serves as an input to this modeling effort. Furthermore, extensive documentation of Apple, the Apple Security guide⁸ and Apple's Documentation Archive,⁹ can be found and was consulted in preparation of the system model. Furthermore, Apple Pay is architecturally similar to other mobile payment systems (e.g. Google Wallet), so it is a good representation of a mobile payment system.

⁷ 9.

⁸ 2.

⁹ 1.

3 *Modeling of Data Flow Diagrams*

The first step in the LINDDUN PRO approach involves modeling the system. In this step, a DFD is created that represents the Apple Pay mobile payment system.

3.1 Data Flow Diagrams

Two distinct DFDs are created to describe the main functionalities of the Apple Pay system.

The first DFD, Figure 1, presents the enrollment process of a credit or debit card in Apple Pay as conducted by the Cardholder. The enrollment phase of Apple Pay is relevant because this is the only stage of the process where the actual debit- or credit-card number of the cardholder is used. A cardholder’s identity can be linked to the card number, which might bring forth problems such as third parties using this for analyzing spending habits. In every other stage, a device account number (DAN) is used as a pseudonym. A DAN is a unique number linked to every card available in the Apple Wallet. A cardholder can add the same card to multiple devices, but the DAN will be different for each device. The DAN ensures that a cardholder’s card information is not stored on the device directly.¹⁰ Understanding how the card information is captured, transmitted, and stored in this first stage is important to assess privacy risks.

The other diagram, Figure 2, illustrates the process when a Cardholder uses their device for contactless payment in a store.

The creation of these DFDs is based on the prior work of Fehr¹¹ was used as a guide, and every interaction between DFD elements was cross-verified in both the Apple Security guide¹² and Apple’s Documentation Archive.¹³

Figure 1: DFD of the card enrolment procedur.

Figure 2: DFD of the general payment flow.

3.2 Data Flows: Step by step

A separate data flow diagram (DFD) is provided for the process to add cards to a mobile wallet (Figure 1), and the payment process itself (Figure 2). The numbers below correspond with the flow numbers in the figures displaying the DFDs.

Card registration. The flow to register and add a payment card to the mobile wallet is shown in Figure 1¹⁴. Step by step, the following activities and data flows take place:

- R1. The Cardholder sends the necessary information to the Apple Wallet app to register a new card. This information includes their full name (as printed on the card), the card number, the expiration date and the CVV code¹⁵ of the card.
- R2. This information is sent to the Card Validation process where the information is first examined and verified, then sent to the back-end (Apple Server).
- R3. The Card Validation process fetches additional local context information from the Link and Provision process, which is shared to the back-end and later used for fraud detection. This deviceContext information includes the device model, the

¹⁴ Before the card registration process can start, the Cardholder must be authenticated and have the right authorization, which not depicted and considered a precondition.

¹⁵ Card verification value. Sometimes, a CVC (Card Verification Code) is used for identical purposes.

Cardholder's phone number, and their approximate location, and is used on the one hand to verify against fraud or anomaly and also to construct a valid dan¹⁶.

¹⁶ Device Account Number

R4. Once the initial validity checks of the card have been performed locally (e.g., the correct formatting of card number, its checksum, validity date must be in the future, etc), the information (as well as the Cardholder's explicit consent on the overall terms and conditions¹⁷) are sent to the Apple Server which is part of the Apple back-end.

¹⁷ Not modeled in the DFD.

R5. Via the Issuer Bank, the CVV code is verified¹⁸.

¹⁸ This verification logic is specific and proprietary to the Issuer Bank.

R6. The Apple Server performs additional verification, anomaly and fraud detection, by submitting the deviceContext data to the Fraud detection process. This emits a risk score, here simplified as a boolean.

R7. The Apple Server constructs a DAN and records the card in the Apple Account DB in the back-end which yields an Apple Wallet Pass File (passFile).

R8 Apple Server submits this Apple Wallet Pass File to the Apple Wallet app.

R9 The Apple Wallet App stores the pass file in Local Storage.

Mobile payment. The payment process, i.e. the process of a Cardholder using a mobile wallet to pay for goods or services in a physical store –as depicted in Figure 2– happens as follows:

1. The Payment Terminal (which resides on point-of-sale (POS) terminal) of the vendor sends the payment request data, consisting of the amount to be paid, a payment token, the beneficiary, and possibly the location, to the Apple Pay app¹⁹.
2. The Apple Pay app presents the transaction information to the Cardholder and obtains both payment confirmation and card selection information.
3. Card details are fetched from the Apple Wallet app, including the DAN to be used in this transaction.
4. Based on these inputs, a One-time Payment Token (OTPT) is generated.
5. The One-time Payment Token (OTPT) is stored in the Apple Wallet app, and this state update is synchronized with and persisted by the Apple Server (steps 5.1 and 5.1.1).

¹⁹ This happens over an NFC communication channel, and thus is only viable when the mobile device is kept close to the payment terminal. This is abstracted in this DFD.

6. The Apple Pay App sends the One-Time Payment Token back to the Payment Terminal, in response to the original payment request.
7. The One-Time Payment Token (OTPT) is stored in the local logs of the Point of Sale.
8. The One-Time Payment Token (OTPT) is forwarded from the external Payment Processor.
9. The One-Time Payment Token (OTPT) is stored in the local logs of the Payment Processor.
10. The Payment Processor forwards the OTPT to the Token Service which extracts the PAN²⁰.
11. The Token Service returns the extracted PAN to the Payment Processor.
12. The Payment Processor forwards the PAN, along with the transaction details over the payment network²¹ to the Issuer Bank to the Issuer Bank in an authorization request.
13. The Issuer Bank uses the received information to authorize the payment and sends back the response to the Payment Processor.
14. The Payment Processor forwards the positive response to Payment Terminal which confirms payment success (e.g., through sound or in a display).

²⁰ Primary account number.

²¹ The payment network itself is not depicted. It is the communication channel that supports flows 10 and 11 in Figure 2.

3.3 Glossary

This glossary provides additional explanation of the different architectural elements depicted in DFDS, i.e. in Figure 1 and Figure 2.

Cardholder The Apple Pay user that is in possession of the physical debit or credit card.

Apple Wallet app A mobile application that allows Cardholders to add, manage, and store, debit and credit cards.²² (Although Cardholders can also use the app to make payments with Apple Pay online, this is not shown on the diagrams as the focus is on NFC payments).

²² 2.

Local Storage The Local Storage used by the Apple pay app and where pass files are kept.

Apple Pay App A mobile application designed to manage Apple Pay hosted by the Secure Element.²³ This application implements payment logic and uses NFC communication to communicate with a Payment Terminal.

²³ 2.

Apple Server This process manages the setup and provisioning of cards in Apple Wallet as well as the access to the cards from the back-end side of the payment solution. The servers are responsible for creating and managing the DANs in the Apple Account DB²⁴ and sending corresponding Apple Wallet Pass files (PassFile) to the Apple Wallet app of the Cardholder. ^{24 2.}

Card Validation This process receives the name, the card number, expiration date and CVV code of the credit or debit card, verifies at the level of the Mobile device if these are correct and if so, relays this information in encrypted format to the Apple Server.

CVV Stands for card verification value. This is a three- or four-digit number printed on the back of a credit card to ensure that the Cardholder is in possession of the physical card.²⁵ ^{25 7.}

DeviceContext Collected by the Link and Provision process on the Mobile device. This data element groups information about the Cardholder's device (hardware/software versions), but also includes iTunes and App Store activity, other information about the Cardholder such as the phone number, and the approximate location of the Cardholder.²⁶ ^{26 2.}

Issuer Bank The bank that issues the debit or credit card linked to Apple Pay, must be part of the Apple Pay network if the Cardholder wants to add a card to Apple Pay. Examples of operational Issuer Banks in Belgium are KBC Bank and Revolut.

Link And Provision DeviceContext information is collected on the mobile device of the Cardholder through this process. This information pertains the device (hardware platform), software versions, and includes the Cardholder's location and phone number. Such DeviceContext information is shared to increase trust of the Cardholder and to detect potentially fraudulent or anomalous activity. If a payment request occurs in for example a suspicious location, the transaction might be denied for fear of fraudulent activity.

One-Time Payment Token (OTPT) Is a token specifically encrypted and created for a specific payment transaction. The OTPT includes the DAN, a token expiration date, the currency of the transaction, the payment amount, and (optionally), the name of the cardholder.²⁷ There is also a one-time-use cryptogram —data that has been encrypted—incorporated in the OTPT,²⁸ which prohibits multiple use of the same token (hence the 'one-time' adjective). ^{27 3.} ^{28 4.}

PassFile . Represents the credit or debit card in the Apple Wallet. A PassFile is a package containing a json-file that defines the

pass, contains the card art, metadata about the card, and supported features. The Pass File also keeps track of the pass state. The pass state keeps track of if the card is currently suspended or if additional information is needed before any payment can be made with Apple Pay.²⁹

²⁹ 2.

PaymentInfo Represent a payment transaction, and consists of the amount and the currency code of the transaction, the source and destination addresses and cryptographic signatures.

Payment Processor A third-party institution or service provider that processes electronic payment transactions between a customer's bank account and a merchant's bank account. It is connected to the payment network.

Secure Element (SE) A secure hardware component that host the Apple Pay App and other applets authorized by payment networks or issuer banks.³⁰ Application executed over the Secure Element are protected by the security features of the Secure Element. Some of these features of the Secure Element are: cryptographically secure random number generation, cryptographic services, secure execution of software modules, and secure time measurements.³¹

³⁰ 2.

³¹ 12.

Payment Terminal An application that runs on the point-of-sales device and facilitates mobile payments via Near-Field Communication (NFC), and other business operations.

Payment logs Local logs (persistence unit) of the Point-of-Sales device.

Payment Processor logs Local transaction log (persistence unit) of the payment processor.

Token Service This process is responsible for verifying the One-Time Payment Tokens (OTPT). This process is offered by the Token service provider (TSP).

3.4 Card Number Representations

There are different numbers and identifiers which represent the card of a cardholder during the mobile payment process: the PAN, the DAN, and the OTPT.

The PAN (primary account number) of a debit or credit card is issued by the Issuer Bank. This number consists of maximum 19 digits and follows the ISO/IEC 7812-1:2017³² standard. There are three main components to the PAN:³³

³² 10.

³³ 9.

1. **Issuer Identification Number (IIN):** This is a six-digit number identifying the issuer bank. This number is used for routing a transaction to the correct issuer for authorization. For the routing purpose this number is not encrypted.
2. **Individual Account Number:** This number can range from seven to twelve digits in length. It is the unique identifier of a client's account within the issuer bank.
3. **Check Digit:** One digit used for error detection. It is calculated using the Luhn algorithm.³⁴ This digit helps to detect errors in data entry, such as typing mistakes. 34 8.

The DAN (device account number) is a unique number linked to a specific device for a particular card by Apple. The DAN is created during the card registration phase. It is encrypted and stored in the back-end, such that Apple itself cannot directly access this number.³⁵ This DAN is used within the Apple Pay ecosystem as a replacement of the PAN. 35 2.

The OTPT (one-time payment token) is a unique, single-use token that is generated for each transaction. The OTPT is sent to a merchant instead of the PAN or the DAN.³⁶ The tokenization process ensures that the actual card details are never shared with the merchant or transmitted over the network. 36 11.

During the enrolment phase, the PAN is provided to Apple's servers, and a corresponding DAN is created and stored on the device. When a payment is made using Apple Pay, the OTPT is generated such that the DAN can be obtained or extracted through de-tokenization.³⁷ The token is sent to the merchant and used to process the payment with the payment network. The token is translated back into the corresponding PAN and processed via the payment network with the Issuer Bank. 37 4.

Part II

Privacy threat models

4 Privacy Threats

The table below lists the privacy threats that were established on basis of multi-rater consensus (consensus level shown in final column). The specific LINDDUN threat characteristics used are shown in the penultimate column.

Threat location	Embraced threat description	Characteristics	Consensus
LINKING			
1. requestPayment (amount, paymentToken, beneficiary, location)	The Apple Pay app can link and analyse information for user profiling. The token could serve as an identifier; The amount and location could be used to profile a group of individuals (high amount and near locations could mean "rich" people); location is included, revealing that the cardholder is/has been in this location.	L.2.2.1; L.1.1; L.2.2.2; L.2.1.1	3
10. authorizationRequest (paymentInfo)	PaymentInfo contains all direct unique identifiers of the cardholder and POS. Addresses in info allow linking of both customer and seller to other sales with same addresses. The bank can use and derive many insights with authorization requests and can perform different types of user/group profiling. The amount and location could be used to profile a group of individuals (high amount and near locations could mean "rich" people).	L.1.1; L.2.2; L.2.2.2; L1.1	4
5. store OTPT	The OTPT could be linked to an individual user if decrypted. OTPT links multiple purchases to dan/card. Apple server can link the spending patterns, to locations, to transactions and can gain much private data of the users.	L.1.1; L.2.2	3
5.1. store (OTPT)	Apple has all data stored. The OTPT could be linked to an individual user if decrypted. OTPT links multiple purchases to dan/card.	L.1.1; L2.2; L.2.2.1; L.2.2.2	4
7. submitOTPT (OTPT)	Payment processor has all data available. The OTPT could be linked to an individual user if decrypted. OTPT links multiple purchases to dan/card.	L.1.1; L.2.2.1; L.2.2.2	3

R1. registerCard (name, cardNb, Exp, CVV)	All cardholder information are being processed. Card details could serve as a quasi-identifier. Name enables linking to individual. These are all unique attributes that are revealed to the Apple Wallet app.	L.1.1; L.2.1.1	3
R4. registerCard (name, cardNb, Exp, CVV, deviceContext)	Combining card details with device context can reveal where and how a user is spending time and money. It can be a serious privacy violation. Name enables linking to individual. All cardholder information are being processed. Also multiple quasi-identifier are combined (device context) and profiling is made possible by this.	L.1.1; L.2.1.1; L.2.2.1	4

IDENTIFYING

1. requestPayment(amount, paymentToken, beneficiary, location)	PII is requested by the sales system that will be further processed by both Apple and the merchant/vendor. Beneficiary and location information are identifying. The payment token is unique to the payment and person.	I.2.2; I.1.1; I.2.1.1	4
3. getCardDetails (cardID): cardDetails	The DAN as a unique identifier. card details together reveal information.	I.2.2, I.2.1.1	3
5. store OTPT	Users can be identified by Apple using the card details, OTPT, and other metadata. OTPT contains the name of the cardholder.	I.1.1, I.1.2	3
5.1. store (OTPT)	Users can be identified by Apple using the card details, OTPT, and other metadata. OTPT contains the name of the cardholder.	I.1.1, I.1.2, I.2.1.1	4
6. sendOTPT (OTPT)	Cardholder name is (optionally) included in OTPT.	I.1.1; I.2.1.3	3
7. submitOTPT (OTPT)	Cardholder name is (optionally) included in OTPT.	I.1.1; I.2.1.3	3
R1. registerCard (name, cardNb, Exp, CVV)	The name is an identifier and the cardNb is an identifying pseudonym. The card registration details make the user easily identifiable by the Apple wallet app. The name of the cardholder is needed; the other attributes can be linked to a subject. All details of cardholder are included in this processing.	I.1.1; I.2.1.1; I.2.1.2	4
R4. registerCard (name, cardNb, Exp, CVV, deviceContext)	The card details and the device context are shared with the Apple server, which makes it very easy for the Apple systems to identify any specific user. All details of cardholder are included in this processing, including revealing attributes that are part of the device context (location). The name of the cardholder is needed; the other attributes can be linked to a subject. The name is an identifier and the cardNb is an identifying pseudonym. The device context can have identifying data like location and app activity	I.1.1; I.2.1.1; I.2.2; I.1; I.2.1.2; I.1.2	4

R5. verifyCVV (Name, cardNb, Exp, CVV)	Direct identifiers such as Name, Email are propagated. The name of the cardholder is needed; the other attributes can be linked to a subject. The name is an identifier and the cardNb is an identifying pseudonym.	I.1.1; I.2.1; I.2.1.2; I.2.1.1	3
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NON-REPUDIATION

5. store OTPT	OTPT is stored and generated after user confirms payment, which makes it undeniable that a payment procedure has started and was confirmed by the cardholder. OTPT contains transaction details and card details, that is encrypted. The Apple server knows the origin of the transactions and the cardholder based on the OTPT.	Nr.1.1; Nr.1; Nr.2	4
5.1. store (OTPT)	OTPT is stored and generated after user confirms payment, which makes it undeniable that a payment procedure has started and was confirmed by the cardholder. OTPT is encrypted. OTPT is saved in apple back-end, containing payment information that prevents an individual to deny a transaction and being at a POS.	Nr.1.1; Nr.2	3
R8. sendPassFile (PassFile)	The existence of this passfile prevents an individual in denying using the apple pay service. The existence of a PassFile means that the user has a card. The passfile contains data that is directly attributed to the user including past transactions and card use.	Nr.2, Nr.1.1; Nr.1.2	3

DETECTING

1. requestPayment (amount, paymentToken, beneficiary, location)	Through actual physical observation one can deduce that customer uses a mobile payment system and has a credit card.	D.1	4
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DATA DISCLOSURE

1. requestPayment (amount, paymentToken, beneficiary, location)	If the location data is too granular, it will lead to serious privacy violations of the cardholder by disclosing their spending insights to the apple pay app. The location of the payment is data that is/should not be needed by Apple to confirm a physical payment by the user.	DD3.2; DD.1.2; DD.1.3	3
5. store OTPT	The OTPT contains the name of the cardholder, which is not necessary as all the vital information for the payment is already in the DAN and OTPT. Apple server has access to users' transactions and financial activities.	DD2.1; DD3.3; DD.1.1	3
5.1. store (OTPT)	The OTPT contains the name of the cardholder, which is not necessary as all the vital information for the payment is already in the DAN and OTPT. Apple server has access to users' transactions and financial activities. All payment information is collected by apple back-end where it is just stored	DD3.2; DD 3.3; DD1.1; DD2.1	4

7. submitOTPT (OTPT)	Data is made accessible to 3rd parties. Location and other personal data could be collected and retained by the external entities. The OTPT contains the name of the cardholder, which is not necessary as all the vital information for the payment is already in the DAN and OTPT	DD2.1; DD 4.1.1; DD.1.1	3
R4. registerCard (name, cardNb, Exp, CVV, deviceContext)	Device context can reveal a lot of insights about the users, their locations, and other personal details to Apple server and can be used further.	DD3.3	3

UNWARENESS

5. store OTPT	Apple's server keeps a record of all the transactions and stores the card details. A user generally is not aware of where and how all that data is stored and recorded. They also don't control what information that they provide about themselves is stored. Cardholder does not know why or how long Apple retains OTPT containing its transaction information: How can the OTPT be cancelled or erased if payment is cancelled or product is returned? The cardholder might be unaware, that payment details in the form of the OTPT are stored on the device.	U1.1; U.2; U.2.3	4
5.1. store (OTPT)	Apple's server keeps a record of all the transactions and stores the card details. A user generally is not aware of where and how all that data is stored and recorded. The Seller is unaware of sending to apple and storing information. They also dont control what information that they provide about themselves is stored. Cardholder does not know why or how long Apple retains OTPT containing its transaction information: How can the OTPT be cancelled or erased if payment is cancelled or product is returned?	U1.1; U.2; U.2.3; U.2.1	4
R4. registerCard (name, cardNb, Exp, CVV, deviceContext)	The user is not aware that the application collects the device context information with Apple server and if this is further processed or stored somewhere. The user is also lacks control of what type of their personal information is collected from their device and being shared with the Apple servers. The cardholder might not be aware that device context is taken into account when creating a DAN.	U.1.1; U.2.1	4
R5. verifyCVV (Name, cardNb, Exp, CVV)	The user is mostly unaware that their card details are verified by their bank everytime they make a transaction via Apple Pay. The user may be unaware that his bank is contacted when registering.	U.1.1	4

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